
FORMATION OF SPEECH-THINKING ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS STUDYING GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract.

In this article, the author considers the main problems of the formation of speech - thinking activity of students in the process of teaching the German language at a university.

Keywords.

speech -thinking activity, foreign language, teaching German, cognitive process, motivation.

Introduction.

The problem of the development of foreign language abilities in the cognitive process as the basis for the formation of verbal thinking activity of students. One of the successful factors that ensure the formation of speech-thinking activity in teaching a foreign language is the work on the purposeful and consistent development of foreign language abilities of students. Naturally, the personality of each student has its own individual characteristics of mental development, on which the formation of verbal and mental activity depends.

The study of speech and thought activity is interdisciplinary in nature, this phenomenon is considered as a subject of study in such sciences as: pedagogy, psychology, linguistics and psycholinguistics by such scientists as K.D. Ushinsky, S.L. Rubinstein, N.I. Zhinkin, I. A. Zimnyaya, A. A. Leontiev and others.

The study of pedagogical literature reveals that an individual approach to each student in the process of teaching foreign languages in textbooks and programs is not regulated. In this regard, the teacher himself conducts individual training in order to develop abilities for a foreign language.

Main part:

The process of forming the skills of speech-thinking activity occurs not only with the help of mental determinants. This process is also influenced by factors such as the development of will and learning motivation. Strong catalysts for the

development of abilities are goals, emotions, as well as personal needs in learning activities [1,152].

It should be noted that if a student has insufficiently developed abilities for a foreign language, then neither positive educational motivation nor teaching methods can provide him with the formation of a foreign language speech-thinking activity.

For a student, not only the result of educational activity is important, but also the process, that is, the nature of its implementation. As for the teacher, in his assessments he most often focuses on the result of the activity.

The teacher in most cases does not distinguish between the productive and procedural aspects of the assignment by students. Since any abilities develop in activity, a foreign language teacher attaches great importance to personal factors that stimulate a person's mental abilities and organize him to overcome the difficulties of educational activities [3.288].

In the formation of foreign language abilities in students, it is important to note the work of the teacher in developing the intellectual qualities of students, since they contribute to the easy and quick achievement of success in educational activities. Since we consider the foreign language abilities of students as individual psychological characteristics, there is a need for individual work of a foreign language teacher with students.

In individual work, the humanization of learning is carried out, as a manifestation of the attention of higher education to the personality of the student. However, it is known that the unique individuality of each person is made up of a combination of countless properties. It is difficult for a teacher who simultaneously solves many learning tasks in a lesson to take into account all the individual characteristics of students [24, 14]. Therefore, in the process of search work, it is necessary to determine such individual characteristics that are most significant in the formation of the skills of speech-thinking activity in the process of teaching foreign language oral-speech communication and such individual characteristics that are available for diagnosis to the teacher.

As a result of the analysis of literature on psychology and methods of teaching foreign languages, we come to the conclusion that there are the following groups of features that can affect abilities. Features of the orientation of the student's personality: motives, interests, inclinations. Based on them, it is possible to provide a high level of educational and communicative motivation [3, 290]. A group of characteristics, including socio-cultural, age characteristics, communicative

competence, emotionality, temperament, the student's status in the study group, his self-esteem.

Given these features, the teacher can create favorable conditions for pedagogical influence on students, aimed at developing foreign language abilities. Consequently, the means of actualizing the potential capabilities of each student is the mobilization of the reserves of his mental development. With regard to abilities for foreign language speech activity, the individual work of a foreign language teacher should be aimed at systematically taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of the student and at developing foreign language abilities in those who have them underdeveloped.

Observations of the educational process at the university show that the work of foreign language teachers at the university is mainly in the nature of taking into account the individual characteristics of students, which is expressed in a differentiated distribution of tasks of varying degrees of complexity and difficulty. In addition, in the practical work of teachers it is not difficult to determine the different levels of requirements for students' knowledge and the different degree of students' activation in foreign language lessons [33,265]. It should also be noted that not all teachers correctly take into account the age characteristics of students, their level of mental development in educational situations and an individual approach. For example, when analyzing students' homework, it is found that the assignment is given the same difficulty for all students in the class.

Judging by the studied classes, we can conclude that the majority of teachers take into account in their work only the current level of development of students. If a student fails in a foreign language, the teacher classifies him as incapable, seeing his task only in forcing students to work on themselves. Of course, this teacher's approach to teaching students the skills of speech thinking in a foreign language and, in general, to the development of intellectual labor abilities contradicts the principle of humanization of education.

In psychology, it is noted that "where the environment does not create appropriate tasks, does not put forward new requirements, does not induce and stimulate the development of the intellect with the help of new goals, there the thinking of a teenager does not develop all the inherent possibilities, does not reach higher forms or reaches them with extremely late" [30,134]. The above quotation eloquently confirms the idea that activities to develop the student's abilities should not be random, but stimulating with the help of new goals.

If we take in teaching German a simple training in performing the same type of exercises, or voicing ready-made dialogues, or translating sentences from German into Uzbek or Russian, then this only leads to the improvement of the mastered educational material, but does not lead to further development of the mechanisms of mental development. It should be noted that when the question of human abilities is put on the agenda, it is necessary to clarify the essence of the question "The nature of what abilities are we talking about?"

There are abilities as mental properties of a person, which are the result of development and education. At the same time, there is the concept of ability, representing the psychological properties of the nervous system, which are only the natural basis for the development of abilities. In our study, we are talking about abilities as mental properties of the student's personality, which are the result of development and education in the educational process during the psychophysiological study of individual characteristics of perception, attention, memory, imagination, thinking, speech [34, 25].

Memory, one of the main conditions of mental life, plays an important role in the development of abilities to master foreign speech. Memory is included in the structure of the intellect and is also included in the general ability to learn, to learn, as a necessary condition for the accumulation of a fund of knowledge and intellectual skills.

Conclusion:

Thus, taking into account all of the above, when designing a lesson with students, the teacher needs to implement methodological methods that speed up and facilitate the student's learning of German. With the first successes achieved in the work, interest usually arises in the very process of learning a non-native language and unfamiliar speech. The student usually consciously shows strong-willed efforts to master foreign language material, based on the real possibilities of mastering a foreign language.

Optimal methods of memorizing speech units, correct orientations in working on foreign texts, observance of the necessary principles when constructing utterances in a foreign language contribute to the formation of the core skills of speech-thinking activity. These rudiments of skills will gradually lead not only to the development of the ability to build correct sentences in German, but will also speed up the process of forming foreign language abilities at the level of verbal-thinking activity.

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